

Burnout and coping strategies among health sciences academicians: Preliminary Study

Fatma Kantaş Yılmaz

University of Health Sciences, Türkiye

Purpose

The responsibilities of academics have immensely increased from teaching, course management and student counselling to conducting research, obtaining research grants, publishing papers for conferences and journals, and serving on committees for student affairs. Many academics have experienced a work-life imbalance and problems associated with this change because they are now expected to devote a significant amount of time and immense effort to these multiple obligations (Zakaria and Asmawi, 2015; Levin, 1991; Jaschik, 2013). The increasing pressure on academicians to produce research and publications and take on administrative tasks has led to work stress and burnout which can have a negative impact on their well-being and job satisfaction.

Burnout is an increasing problem and negatively impacts an individual's job satisfaction and physical and mental health. Burnout is defined as a syndrome of emotional exhaustion, depersonalization and reduced sense of personal accomplishment at work (Maslach and Jackson, 1981; Burke, 1995). Coping strategy is important to handle with difficult conditions, it can be defined as a person's active effort to decrease stress and create new methods of handling situations at each life stage (Grace, 2014).

This study aimed to investigate burnout and coping strategies among health science academicians at a state university in Istanbul, Türkiye. To our knowledge, this preliminary study is the first attempt at evaluating this problem among health science academicians.

Design

Study design and participants

All health science academicians (n=74) were invited to fill out the self-administered questionnaire through investigators. The current study was designed as a cross-sectional study and carried out in the Health Science Faculty of the University of Health Sciences in İstanbul, Türkiye. A 59-item questionnaire was administered to 54 academicians of the health science faculty. The survey was administered during the spring term of the 2022-23 academic year (March 2023).

Data Collection Tools

The data collection tools comprised three parts, including 5 items for sociodemographic data, 22 items for the Maslach Burnout Inventory–Educators Form and 32 items for R-COPE Turkish Version. R-COPE Turkish Version includes 5 subscales (self-help, approach, accommodation, avoidance, and self-punishment) with a 4-point Likert-type scale (Dicle and Ersanlı, 2015). Maslach Burnout Inventory-Educator Form (MBI-EF) has three subdimension: emotional exhaustion (9 items), depersonalization (5 items), and personal accomplishment (8 items) (Maslach and Jackson, 1981).

Data analysis

Data were analysed with SPSS for Windows 27.00 program. Descriptive statistics were used for the number and frequency of categories. Demographic characteristics were compared with the Kruskal Wallis H test and Mann Whitney U test for non-parametric data. Pearson Correlation was used to determine the relationships between the two scales. The significance level was set at a $p < 0.05$.

Results

Sample Characteristics

The overall characteristics of the participants are summarized in Table 1. The average age of 54 participants was 33.5 ± 7.5 years, and 72.2% were women. The majority of participants had a research assistant degree and a single status.

Table 1. Demographic characteristics of the participants (n=54)

Variables	Group	n	(%)
Gender	Female	39	72.2
	Male	15	27.8
Marital status	Single	32	59.3
	Married	22	40.7
Work duration	1-5 year	35	64.8
	6-10 year	12	22.2
	>11 years	7	13.0
Title	Research Assistant	24	44.4
	Associate Professor /Professor	8	14.8
	Assistant Professor	13	24.1
	Lecturer	9	16.7
Age (years)	Mean 33.5 ± 7.5		

Table 2 showed that the majority of participants had low level of emotional exhaustion and depersonalization and high level of personal accomplishment.

Table 2. Burnout Level

Sub-dimensions	Low level (n)	Moderate level (n)	High level (n)
Emotional exhaustion	25	17	12
Depersonalization	49	3	2
Personal accomplishment	19	13	22

The mean scores of MBI-EF sub-scales, including emotional exhaustion, depersonalization and personal accomplishment, did not differ significantly by gender. However, R-COPE scale scores were significantly higher in female participants (86.58 ± 8.30) than in male participants (82.13 ± 4.73) ($p = .024 < 0.05$). Female participants also had higher scores on the self-help dimension (Table 3).

There were no significant differences for MBI-EF and R-COPE sub-scales based on the frequency of marital status, work duration and title.

Table 3. The distribution of scales scores according to gender

Scales	Gender	n	Mean	SS	z	Sd	p
Emotional exhaustion	F	39	19.25	11.69	-.937	52	.349
	M	15	15.93	10.47			
Depersonalization	F	39	2.43	3.39	-1.538	52	.124
	M	15	4.86	5.46			
Personal accomplishment	F	39	32.02	8.87	-.367	52	.713
	M	15	32.80	11.29			
R-COPE	F	39	86.58	8.30	-2.264	52	.024*
	M	15	82.13	4.73			
Self-help	F	39	19.02	3.64	-2.697	52	.007*
	M	15	15.86	3.46			
Approach	F	39	23.89	2.95	-.651	52	.515
	M	15	23.26	3.10			
Accommodation	F	39	21.43	3.25	-.525	52	.600
	M	15	20.66	3.17			
Avoidance	F	39	9.61	2.94	-1.660	52	.097
	M	15	11.13	3.02			

Self-punishment	F	39	12.61	4.37	-1.145	52	.252
	M	15	11.20	3.80			

*Significance level 0.05. F=female, M=male

Table 4 summarizes the correlations between the variables analysed in the study. The MBI-EF Depersonalization Scale showed weak and negative correlations with overall R-COPE ($r=-.370$; $p=.021$), self-help ($r=-.334$; $p=.014$), approach ($r=-.368$; $p=.006$), accommodation ($r=-.321$; $p=.018$) dimensions. The overall R-COPE showed strong correlations with the accommodation ($r=.680$; $p=.000$), and moderate correlations with self-help ($r=.493$; $p=.000$) and approach ($r=.531$; $p=.000$) dimensions. The personal accomplishment sub-scale showed a weak correlation with age ($r=.276$; $p=.043$).

Table 4. Correlation Analysis

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Emotional exhaustion (1)	1									
Depersonalization (2)	.478**	1								
Personal accomplishment (3)	-.255	-.312*	1							
R-COPE (4)	-.129	-.370**	.217	1						
Self-help (5)	-.089	-.334*	.403**	.493**	1					
Approach (6)	-.226	-.368**	.381**	.531**	.320*	1				
Accommodation (7)	-.292	-.321*	.432**	.680**	.416**	.577**	1			
Avoidance (8)	.215	.219	-.389**	.181	-.400**	-.356**	-.092	1		
Self-punishment (9)	.074	-.024	-.291*	.353**	-.265	-.213	-.239	.301*	1	
Age variable (10)	-.078	-.097	.276*	.085	-.077	.093	.083	-.075	.149	1

Implications

The current study provided insight into burnout and coping strategies among health sciences academicians. Fortunately, the majority of participants had a low level of emotional exhaustion

and depersonalization and a high level of personal accomplishment. In line with previous studies, female academicians had higher overall R-COPE scores and the self-help dimension score. The overall R-COPE showed strong correlations with the accommodation and moderate correlations with self-help and approach dimensions.

Universities should take proactive measures to address academician burnout by offering resources and support as well as enacting work-life balance policies. Universities should therefore support academicians in managing their workload and lowering levels of work stress, enhancing their wellbeing and job satisfaction.

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Resources

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